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ECT2L, activated during EMT and dissemination, interacts with an ERBB gene product.

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We previously described the existence of an alternative isoform of the major solid tumor gene product ECT2, ECT2L, and its transcriptional induction during metastasis. We report here that ECT2L appears to cooperate with an ERBB (HER/EGFR) family member, *HER4*, and interact with the Ras pathway to drive transformation and/or colonization at a distant organ site.

Results

I. ECT2L cooperation with HER4 (*ERBB4*) revealed by study of transcriptional co-regulation at the systems level across multiple tissues in humans.

Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	P-Value	Description
ECT2L	345930	-3.2000	0.9996	epithelial cell transforming sequence 2 oncogene-like

Coexpressed genes:

84	ERBB4	2066	0.6008	0.0014	v-erb-a erythroblastic leukemia viral oncogene homolog 4 (avian)
1450	TOB1	10140	0.2925	0.0818	transducer of ERBB2, 1
2196	ERBB2	2064	0.2386	0.1154	v-erb-b2 erythroblastic leukemia viral oncogene homolog 2, neuro/glioblastoma derived oncogene homolog (avian)

II. Potential cooperation between Ras pathway components with ERBB4 and ECT2L.

Systems level query revealed co-regulation of *DIRAS3* with ERBB4 and ECT2L (Figure 2a).

Figure 2a. *DIRAS3* is a ERBB4 and ECT2L co-regulated gene product.

Among the genes whose expression was mostly closely co-regulated with DIRAS3, ERBB4 and ECT2L were the Ras pathway components and Ras-related genes, as well as the estrogen-related receptor gamma *ESRRG* and tyrosine kinase *NTRK2* (Figure 2b).

Figure 2b. Potential cooperation between Ras pathway components with ERBB4 and ECT2L.

Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value
ERBB4	2066	-0.2942	0.0603
DIRAS3	9077	-0.4612	0.0034
ECT2L	345930	-320.0000	-320.0000

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	%Co-reg (transcriptome-wide)
1	NTRK2	4915	0.8410	0.0001	
18	ESRRG	2104	0.6810	0.0003	
447	RASSF9	9182	0.4507	0.0040	
538	RERGL	79785	0.4338	0.0018	
914	CNKSR2	22866	0.3821	0.0064	
1012	RASSF10	644943	0.3683	0.0000	
1052	RASL12	51285	0.3639	0.0390	
1188	RADIL	55698	0.3513	0.0116	

Out of 17779 total transcripts

Discussion

We described here cooperation of an isoform of the major solid tumor gene product, ECT2, ECT2L, with a member of the EGFR/ERBB gene family, ERBB4 (HER4). Genes of the Ras oncogene family including RASSF9 and RASSF10 were identified as ECT2L/ERBB4 interacting genes at the level of transcriptional co-regulation.